

IRIS

MAIN COLORS

CMYK = C58 M82 Y0 K0
RGB = R127 G79 B159
7F4F9F

CMYK = C74 M60 Y0 K0
RGB = R84 G108 B178
546CB2

CMYK = C50 M40 Y40 K5
RGB = R131 G133 B135
838587

ADDITIONAL COLORS

CMYK = C38 M28 Y55 K0
RGB = R166 G163 B129
A6A381

CMYK = C62 M47 Y0 K0
RGB = R101 G133 B230
6585E6

CMYK = C0 M20 Y18 K0
RGB = R255 G212 B196
ffd4c4